

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF THE ART OF VOCAL PERFORMANCE IN THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi mustaqillikka erishgandan so'ng, san'atning vokal ijrochiligi yo'nalishidagi islohotlar va rivojlanish bosqichlari haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xonanda, vokal, san'at, diafragma, ijro, nafas olish, tovush, tendensiya, metodologiya, "yashirin" nafas, nafassiz kuylash, soha rivoji.

Аннотация: В данной статье после обретения независимости Республики Узбекистан рассматриваются технологии развития и управления в сфере вокального исполнительства.

Ключевые слова: певец, вокал, искусство, диафрагма, исполнение, дыхание, звуки, направление, методика, «скрытое» дыхание, бездыханное пение, развитие поля.

Abstract: In this article, after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development and management technologies in the field of vocal performance are discussed.

Key words: singer, vocal, art, diaphragm, performance, breathing, sounds, trend, methodology, "hidden" breath, breathless singing, field development.

Processes of formation of musical culture in Uzbekistan, new styles in music, the role and importance of national instruments in the development of musical culture, classical folk music, traditional professional music, folk compositional ways, as well as folklore - amateur musical It is certainly gratifying to see performances that are close to each other in terms of form and style, as well as this musical heritage as a part of our spiritual culture today. It is no secret that vocals, which have taken the main place in the field of singing, are now very popular. The tradition of dividing vocals into traditional, classical and Estrada types came to our country from highly developed countries. Physiological nature of vocals produces methods of voice development based on human physiology common to all ethnicities and cultures. This allows Uzbek songs to become popular outside our great country. Our compatriots actively participate in various international contests and festivals, are worthy of the evaluation of the distinguished jury and the applause of the public. Theoretical literature testifies that Italy is the center of European vocal art and historically the oldest. There is a concept of "ekslamatsya" in old written sources.

This term is now almost obsolete. It means "To release the sound first with force, and then to reduce it sharply". In those times, it was used to create sound. Vocal is a unique type of musical art, which is primarily based on mastering the art of singing at a high level. Chanting can be done alone, accompanied by an ensemble or a choir. Importantly, vocal art is now widely used in operas, operettas, musical dramas, comedies, and variety concerts. The main tool in vocals is proper breathing. It is necessary to maintain the correct height in order to realize the performer's breathing. In this case, the back view is *basti*, that is, the spine is well arched in the lumbar region, and the diaphragm is attached to the upper lumbar spine by its swinging muscular ligaments. The lower back is like a tight grip on the contraction of the diaphragm, so the lumbar spine should be strong. Performance is the most complex function of the breath, controlling and correcting exhalation.

It ensures diaphragmatic breathing, corrects the airflow during exhalation, and correctly positions the chest to maintain the performance volume. Performance is an exhalation skill, but not all professionals have it. In the beginning, it would be better if everyone learned not to choose the breath from the first sound sentence, that is, to place it gradually in a smooth flow until the end. It provides a smooth sound. It should not be forgotten that when it comes to the singer's breath, too much attention is paid to it and sometimes the wrong idea is given to singers to control the quality of their voice, intonation, and to pay enough attention to creative moments. Does not allow focusing. For this reason, it is recommended that the novice singer not focus too much on the breathing process. Now, it is impossible to break it. For example: raising the shoulders, pulling out the stomach, excessive movements of the breath, especially taking in too much air, as well as "breathless" singing - singing without breathing support. If the breathing is normal, as mentioned earlier, the singer should pay attention to a beautiful, free sound, remembering that it is always related to the proper functioning of the entire voice-producing apparatus. The following are the practical tips for the room breathing: Before starting to sing, the student's body should be straightened, the stomach should be pulled in, the chest should be slightly raised, and the back and shoulders should be straight. The general mood of the singer implies creative activity, high mood in the state of complete muscle freedom of the whole body, as if a person is pleasantly refreshed. In this case, the lower ribs are expanded in the imagined "Ax", which should be held until the end of fanation.

Breathing should be noiseless (through the nose and slightly open mouth). In a fraction of a second, the breath is caught and begins to sing in this "hidden" breath. It is necessary to save the breath very much and try to maintain the respiratory system (as if continuing to take in air). This allows you to feel the support of the sound. In order to breathe more deeply, the student should be told to imagine that he slowly smells the perfume of his favorite flower. This method is based on the practice of many well-known pedagogic vocalists. Singing breath should be gradually developed and strengthened. Another important skill is the beginning of singing, which is born with the idea of sound attack, preferably a soft but clear attack, that is, without movement and breathing, without a strong blow to the vocal cords. It creates a smooth sound, provides an increasingly beautiful sound timbre, and prevents tissue fatigue.

True, in some cases, for example, if the grain of flour is loose, a strong active attack is used. As a means of expression and for methodical purposes, breathing attacks are sometimes used. Like the beginning of a jarang, its end also demands attention. Inexperienced singers are unable to share their breath, so the end of the phrases sound restless, unstable, and there is no clarity of stopping to "get" the sound. Vocal exercises prepare the singer to perform a piece of art; they work on the elements of vocal skills. One such element is rhythmic organization. Exact and consistent stretching of equal shares, observance of pauses requires a certain lesson. Rhythmic precision must be achieved with rigor. Usually, before singing, the exercise is played at the given tempo and strictly observing all the distances, keeping clear pauses between the syllables of the modulation sequence. It is necessary to develop a sense of rhythm from the first steps of education. This is a very important aspect of the skill training system.

The mood at the beginning of the training, the singer's readiness to sing, and the ability to enter a creative state are of great importance for mastering the tasks ahead. A student with a low inactive tone cannot achieve high results. Focusing attention, fixation of the teacher's instructions, creative enthusiasm depends primarily on the student himself. This shows his ability and professional qualities. The role of the pedagogue in the necessary psychological adjustment cannot be underestimated. His ability to establish the necessary creative communication and his emotional charge determine the mood of the student. In addition, mastering the diaphragmatic breathing technique helps to ensure that the breath is not interrupted in a smooth, steady flow, and that the speed is good and intense. The sound will be smooth and resonant. The gradual release of air ensures that it turns into resonant sound waves. Knowing how to use the breath

in this way determines that it becomes a sound without any residue, that the exhalation in performance is skillfully mastered. Untrained performers often take in a lot of air when they breathe and spend it on the first sound of a musical phrase. According to the testimony of S. Fuchito, the great singer E. Caruso always trained his breath with special exercises, and strengthened control over air consumption until he reached a high level of proficiency. In conclusion, it can be said that it is impossible to overexert yourself in vocal breathing exercises. Because the sound causes confusion, fatigue, tremors. A singer must know how to make the most of every minute of silence, to rest, to know how to breathe again perfectly actively to overcome fatigue

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